

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1820	Henry Yule	1842		1889		British Scottish Orientalist and geographer	1820-1889
1820	Georg Curtius	1842		1885		German philologist	1820-1885
1820	Herbert Spencer	1851		1903		British English philosopher, biologist, anthropologist, and sociologist known for his infamous theory of social Darwinism throughout contemporary history	1820-1903
1821	Jens Andreas Friis	1844	1844	1896		Norwegian philologist, lexicographer and author	1821-1896
1821	George J. Adler	1845		1868		German-American noted philologist and linguist	1821-1868
1821	Rudolf von Roth	1846		1895		German Indologist, founder of the Vedic philology	1821-1895
1821	August Schleicher	1848		1868		German linguist	1821-1868
1821	Louis Laurent Gabriel de Mortillet	1849		1898		French archeologist and anthropologist	1821-1898
1823	Nayden Gerov	1855		1900		Bulgarian linguist, folklorist, writer and public figure during the Bulgarian National Revival	1823-1900
1823	Robert Hunter	1863		1897		British Scottish the lead editor of the Encyclopædic Dictionary	1823-1897
1823	Michael Heilprin	1873		1888		Polish-American Jewish biblical scholar, critic, and writer	1823-1888
1824	Rudolf Hildebrand	1856		1890		German Germanist, contributor to, and then, editor of the Grimm brothers' Deutsches Wörterbuch	1824-1894